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Impact of COVID on mental health

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Background:

COVID-19, like every other pandemic, has imposed an unprecedented threat to doctors' physical and mental health. Literature in this area is sparse. The present study has been done to explore the knowledge, attitude, and behavior of doctors regarding this pandemic and how it influences their depression, anxiety, and stress level.

Materials and Methods:

This online survey has been done for 10 days. Data were collected on background characteristics, knowledge, attitude, and behavior of the respondents in a semi-structured pro forma, and psychiatric morbidity was measured by the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale-21. A total of 152 complete responses have been received. The data were assessed using SPSS software.

Results:

Out of 152 study participants, 34.9% were depressed and 39.5% and 32.9% were having anxiety and stress, respectively. Significant predictors for psychiatric morbidities were experience in health sector, duty hours, use of protective measures, and altruistic coping. Multivariable logistic regression showed most of the factors to be significantly associated with depression, anxiety, and stress level.

Discussion:

Doctors who were working during COVID pandemic have a high prevalence of psychiatric morbidity. Age and having multiple comorbidities are significant predictive factors. Adequate protective measures should be warranted. Altruistic coping and a sense of greater goal are significant among the doctor community, in this pressing time. The doctors are pushing themselves to the best of their capacity and also protecting their patients' best interest. A large-scale, multicentric study will probably give a larger picture and will guide us for better service planning and delivery.

Reference:

1. American Psychiatric Association, & American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5*. Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publication, 2013.

2. Bech, P., *Rating scales for mood disorders: Applicability, consistency, and construct validity. Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 78(S345), 45–55.10.1111/j.1600-0447.1988.tb08567, 1988.
3. Hamilton, M. A. X., *The assessment of anxiety states by rating. British Journal of Medical Psychology*, 32(1), 50–55.10.1111/j.2044-8341.1959.tb00467, 1959.
4. Liu, Q., Luo, D., Haase, J. E., Guo, Q., Wang, X. Q., Liu, S., ... Yang, B. X. . *The experiences of health-care providers during the COVID-19 crisis in China: A qualitative study. The Lancet Global Health*, 8, e790–798, 2020.
5. Roy, D., Tripathy, S., Kar, S. K., Sharma, N., Verma, S. K., & Kaushal, V. (2020). *Study of knowledge, attitude, anxiety & perceived mental healthcare need in Indian population during COVID-19 pandemic. Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 51, 102083.10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102083, 2020.
6. Wang, C., Pan, R., Wan, X., Tan, Y., Xu, L., Ho, C. S., & Ho, R. C. (2020). *Immediate psychological responses and associated factors during the initial stage of the 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19) epidemic among the general population in China. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(5), 1729.10.3390/ijerph1705172
7. World Health Organization, *Global influenza strategy 2019–2030. World Health Organization*, 2019.